

Modeling protonated retinal C=N stretching in ChannelRhodopsin2

Envelope work report by
Dr. Matteo Capone

Principal Investigator:
Dr. Laura Zanetti-Polzi

Channel-Rhodopsin2 Function

Channel-Rhodopsin-2 (**ChR2**) is a light-gated cation-selective **ion channel**

Photo-isomerization of the retinal cofactor induces the channel opening

ChR2 is one of the most used **optogenetic tool** in neurosciences

Mutation influence on photo-cycle

Residue **mutations** which influence hydrogen bond network (HBN) have shown **strong effect on function and kinetic of the photo-cycle(PC)**.

Arginine 120 links retinal to the exit of the ion channel. R120H mutation provides an active photo-cycle, but no channel opening.

Mutation influence on photo-cycle

Differential and time-resolved IR spectroscopy has been used to track **conformational changes** along the photo-cycle

1580 and 1664 cm^{-1} : **Amide modes**
1655, 1638 cm^{-1} : retinal **C=N stretching**

Retinal FTIR in organic solvent

TRSB (0.1M)	C=O		C=N		C=C	C=NH ⁺		C=C ⁺		COO ⁻	
	cm ⁻¹	(A)	cm ⁻¹	(A)		cm ⁻¹	(A)	cm ⁻¹	(A)	cm ⁻¹	(A)
ASPB CHCl ₃	1709	0.67	1619 sh	0.21	h	1657	0.27	1564 sh	0.52	1580	0.27
10% MeOH + 90% CHCl ₃	1706	0.61	1619 sh	0.27	h	1655	0.36	1561 sh	0.67	1588 sh	0.41
50% MeOH + 50% CHCl ₃	1697	0.56	1619 sh	0.27	h	1649	0.45	1555 sh	0.89	1589 sh	0.54
100% MeOH	1695	0.51	h		h	1649	0.47	1555 sh	0.90	1593 sh	0.62

Retinal simulation org. solvent

Retinal + Counterion in CHCl_3

Retinal + Counterion in MeOH

Retinal flexibility in org. solvent

In both solvents, the structure of the retinal is heavily distorted from planarity. In particular **C6-C7**, **C8-C9**, **C10-C11** and **C11-C12**

Retinal dihedral distribution in MM-MD

FF: Charmm36

Parm. gen: CHARMM-GUI

Retinal flexibility in org. solvent

Both simulations start from fully planar configuration

FF: Amber14

DFT: PBE/DZVP

The C6-C7 and C14-C15 are slightly different in the two solvents.

The HB distance with the counter ion in MeOH is maintained along the MD

PMM for IR spectra calculation

QMMM Optimization in org. solvent

DFT: B3LYP/DZVP

QMMM opt in CHCl_3

C6-C7 : -163.63
C8-C9 : 179.86
C10-C11 : -176.55
C12-C13 : -172.06
C14-C15 : -178.81

QMMM opt in MeOH

C6-C7 : -168.96
C8-C9 : -175.05
C10-C11 : 170.02
C12-C13 : 172.60
C14-C15 : 177.31

NMA from QMMM optimization

Retinal from QMMM opt in CHCl₃

C6-C7	: -163.63
C8-C9	: 179.86
C10-C11	: -176.55
C12-C13	: -172.06
C14-C15	: -178.81

Gas-phase NMA → C=N at 1621 cm⁻¹

NMA from QMMM optimization

Retinal from QMMM opt in MeOH

C6-C7 : -168.96
C8-C9 : -175.05
C10-C11 : 170.02
C12-C13 : 172.60
C14-C15 : 177.31

Gas-phase NMA → C=N at 1623 cm⁻¹

NMA from QMMM optimization

Retinal from QMMM opt in CHCl₃

Retinal from QMMM opt in MeOH

C=N Mode in Organic Solvent

DFT: **B3LYP**

Basis set: **6-31+g***

Gas-phase C=N: **$\sim 1622 \text{ cm}^{-1}$**

Exp. : **$[1657-1649] = +8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$**

Theo. : **$[1641-1629] = +12 \text{ cm}^{-1}$**

Retinal Pocket Comparison

Wildtype

R120H

WT vs R120H backbone fluctuation

Retinal flexibility in ChR2

FF: Amber14

Ret Parm gen: QMD-FF (Ardevol et al.)

The retinal is very rigid and the protein mutation is not able to affect its flexibility

Retinal interactions on MM-MD

Retinal Schiff-base interactions

R120/H120 interactions on MM-MD

ARG/HIS-120

R120/H120 interactions on MM-MD

ARG/HIS-120

K93 interactions on MM-MD

LYS-93

NMA from QMMM optimization

Retinal from QMMM opt in ChR2-WT

C6-C7	: 164.04
C8-C9	: -174.54
C10-C11	: -175.20
C12-C13	: -176.19
C14-C15	: -175.04

Gas-phase NMA \rightarrow C=N at 1693 cm^{-1}

C=N Mode in ChR2

DFT: **B3LYP**

Basis set: **6-31+g***

Gas-phase C=N: **~1627 cm⁻¹**

Exp

WT: 1657 cm⁻¹

R120H : 1657/1660 cm⁻¹

Theo.

WT: 1630 cm⁻¹

R120HIE: 1625 cm⁻¹

R120HIP: 1630 cm⁻¹

